

Enhancing the Learning Process of Folk Dances using Augmented Reality and Non-Invasive Brain Stimulation

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Abstract

Dancing is a very popular entertainment activity which is, however, quite difficult to learn. Our objective is to facilitate the traditional dance-learning process – based on imitating teacher’s movements – by employing current technological advances. In particular, we record professional dancers’ performances using a motion capture system and display the recorded data as moving avatars within a developed mobile-phone application. This application in combination with the mobile phone used as a headset, allows students to observe professional dancing within an augmented-reality environment. To demonstrate the benefits of such environment, we show that students can learn dancing when using the developed application. We assess the dancing quality by determining a similarity with respect to professional performance, based on the Dynamic Time Warping applied to the recorded motion capture data. Also, we analyze the effect of transcranial direct current stimulation (tDCS) on motor learning. We experimentally demonstrate that students with received tDCS perform dancing significantly better. We evaluate all the experiments on a real-life dataset of folk dances.

Keywords: folk dance, motion capture, brain stimulation, tDCS, augmented reality

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1. Introduction

Folk dances as part of intangible cultural heritage (ICH) represent an important part of the cultural identity of the society. Usually, they are learned

informally and transmitted to the next, younger generations. Nowadays, new,
5 modern, digital technologies are widely spread and available for different pur-
poses, including folk dances digitization and visualization. On the other hand,
augmented reality (AR) can support and offer functionalities like examination
from different viewpoints and angles, play/pause, divide dances into steps, play
forward/backward, change the speed. It can also include several different dances
10 and offer male and female versions of the dance or even virtual partner. Another
advantage of these applications is providing feedback to the user, which can be
beneficial for learning. Feedback is usually offered based on a comparison of the
data from the user and data from the professional dancer. For data recording,
motion capture systems are used. AR applications can be used whenever a user
15 wants to learn and practice the dance, and this way, learning procedure can be
organized according to their pace and preferences. The goal of these applica-
tions is not to replace the teacher, but to provide a different way of learning
and facilitate that process.

Transcranial direct current stimulation (tDCS) has already been success-
20 fully applied to enhance motor learning with healthy individuals. It has also
been applied for motor recovery after pathological states associated with motor
deficits [1]. In the past decades [2], research interest for tDCS has increased and
become popular since it allows electrical modulation of the neurons that can re-
sult in accelerating learning and determination of brain regions involved in the
25 process of motor learning [3]. Folk dances include significant limb movements
and we recognized the potential to use tDCS before the learning procedure to
improve the dance performance. For motor tasks, including dance learning, it
is characteristic that practice and repetition performance can improve [4].

The objective of this article is to investigate the influence of the non-invasive
30 brain stimulation (tDCS) in combination with the AR application to dance
learning performance. To the best of our knowledge, this combination has not
been presented in the literature yet. In focus of our work is following: acquisi-
tion of the motion data and assessing the quality of the dance performances by
measuring similarity with respect to professional dancers (Section 3.1); interac-

35 tive AR application with folk dances in a male and female version (Section 3.2);
sham-controlled user study, where half of the participants receive tDCS and
all the participants have to learn a folk dance (Section 3.4). Avatars with the
prerecorded animation data from professional dancers were created and added
to the AR application used in combination with a mobile phone. Further, the
40 mobile phone was used as a head-mounted display to allow users to observe pro-
fessional dancers' movements in AR environment. The procedure presented in
this work was tested with ten healthy participants without prior experience in
dancing and their task was to learn one particular folk dance. Each participant
attended three sessions that included the same procedure. Before the learning
45 task, tDCS or sham was applied using small direct current and two sponge elec-
trodes placed over the region of interest. After the stimulation part, participants
had a minute to practice the interaction with the application on mobile phone,
and afterwards, they attempted to the learning task. The learning task included
two parts; learning only steps of the dance and learning the whole dance. In
50 each session, participants had limited time for learning. When the learning task
was done, participants were asked to perform the dance three times with only
music playing. They were recorded using an optical motion capture system with
passive markers, and their data were compared to the data from the professional
dancers using Dynamic Time Warping (DTW). When the experiment was done,
55 participants were asked to fill several post-experiment questionnaires, including
Simulation Sickness (SSQ), Presence Questionnaires (PQ), NASA Task Load
Index (NASA-TLX). Our hypothesis was that the participants that received
tDCS would perform better in the final task. In Figure 1, the workflow of the
entire procedure is illustrated.

60 **2. Related Work**

Analysis of motion capture data and measuring similarity has applications
in many different fields like sport, security, medicine, human-computer interac-
tion, and entertainment. Measuring similarity can be a difficult task as motion

Figure 1: Workflow of the proposed setup.

action can be performed in different ways, e.g., at a different speed, by different
 65 actors, or it can have different length [5]. There is no global method established
 for human motion comparison since similarity is application dependent [6]. An
 extensive survey on content-based management of human motion data can be
 found in [7]. Distance-based functions can be used for comparison of motion
 features similarity. A widely used function is Dynamic Time Warping (DTW).
 70 DTW has been used for measuring the similarity between time signals and has
 applications in different fields, e.g., gesture and movement recognition. In [8],
 DTW has been used for comparison, analysis, and visualization of similarities
 in body joints 3D trajectories. For computing the distance between two dance
 movements obtained under different conditions - with and without music, DTW
 75 was used in [1]. Also, variations of DTW, e.g., Multi-Dimensional DTW(MD-
 DTW), Quaternion DTW (QDTW), can be used for measuring similarities be-
 tween multi-dimensional time series or quaternions [9, 10]. The drawback of this
 algorithm is its quadratic complexity. Some other distance-based approaches
 include Euclidean distance [11], Bhattacharyya distance [12], or Mahalanobis
 80 distance-based DTW [13].

AR applications have been in use for dance preservation and learning [14]. These applications are often combined with motion capture systems and they can provide feedback for the users. The idea of having a mirror in AR where users can see and track their movements is presented by [15]. This way, visual
85 feedback is provided to the users. In another research, AR is used to present a virtual dancer as an instructor or a dance partner. The user could also see their movements as an external observer [16]. In [17], a tool for simulated dancing was proposed. Smart glasses are used for the projection of the virtual dancers in the environment. A live performance with augmented stage and dance as a use case
90 was presented by [18]. In the prototype of the AR application presented in [19], the avatar of a professional dancer is shown to the users. In this application there is no need to complete one step in order to proceed with the learning. The learning procedure can be adjusted to the pace of each user. Also, music is provided, so participants can synchronize their movements according to it.

95 Regarding the connection between tDCS and dances, Kaski et al. [20] applied tDCS in a patient with moderate Parkinson's disease during tango dancing. The patient went through tDCS and sham sessions and results show an increase in overall gait velocity and peak pitch trunk velocity with tDCS. Further, [21] investigated regional brain activity in healthy participants when they played a
100 dance video game with the dominant hand and foot. As we can see, the work presented in this article is a unique combination of AR application and tDCS with the use case in folk dances.

Non-invasive brain stimulation techniques have been used for motor learning, including learning of motor sequence or visuo-motor coordination. Transcranial
105 direct-current stimulation is a non-invasive, neuromodulatory technique that involves the delivery of a low-intensity direct current between two sponge electrodes. Electrodes are usually moistened with NaCl solution. The active electrode is placed on the region of the brain that will be stimulated while the other one is placed contralaterally. Size of the electrodes can vary between 5-35 cm²
110 [22]. The smaller size will provide more focused stimulation, while larger ones will ensure that the entirety of the region of interest is stimulated [23]. Both,

anodal and cathodal tDCS have been studied in the past few years. Anodal tDCS, used in this research, is associated with enhancement of the stimulated area. On the other hand, cathodal tDCS is known as the inhibitory brain stimulation method [24]. TDCS has an application in the enhancement of motor skill learning in healthy humans [22]. Motor skill learning includes different forms of learning, like error-based and reinforcement [25]. It also refers to the process whereby practicing movements are executed more accurately and efficiently [26]. Low currents applied for periods 10-13 minutes can induce cortical excitability changes lasting up to 90 minutes [27].

One of the principal brain areas involved in motor function is the primary motor cortex (M1) and many studies involved it for motor learning processes using tDCS [28, 29]. In [30], effects of anodal tDCS in learning of whole-body dynamic balancing task were investigated. Anodal tDCS was applied over the leg area of the primary motor cortex for 20 minutes and the direct current was set to 1mA. Anode was placed over the bilateral M1 leg area and the cathode was placed over the right frontal orbit. The effect of non-invasive stimulation on motor skill task was performed in [31]. Again, tDCS was applied over M1 and subjects had to practice the task over five consecutive days. Further, effects of tDCS were investigated for motor adaptation [32]. It was hypothesized that anodal tDCS over M1 and premotor cortices would increase the size and duration of the locomotor aftereffect. The duration of the stimulation was 15 minutes and the current was 2mA. Cerebellar tDCS was included in the task of learning the posture and balance [33]. The task required highly coordinated, whole-body movements. Subjects had to hold a stability platform in a horizontal position as long as possible. The stimulation was 10 minutes long.

Moreover, tDCS has been applied to the motor learning skill of the upper limb [34]. TDCS was applied immediately prior to the motor task and participants had to perform the exoskeleton-based training for the left arm. Another task that included upper limb, non-dominant hand, in combination with tDCS, was presented in [35]. M1 region was stimulated for 20 minutes and in the end, there was a significantly increased motor skill learning compared to the sham.

Anodal tDCS can be used for stimulation of the primary motor cortex that may play a role in the motor adaptation of arm reaching when novel physical environments are experienced [36].
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Stimulation can be applied in different stages of the experiment, e.g., prior to or during the learning or training. In the literature, it is mostly applied during the learning [37], [38], [39]. Kaminski et al. [40] applied it only during the first 20 minutes of learning. It can be also applied during the adaptation [36], [41], while some researchers also includes it during the pre-adaptation [42],
150 [43]. In [35], stimulation after the first learning block was applied and in [34] stimulation was applied prior to learning.

Dance is a performing art and has an impact on our minds and bodies. The intersection of brain sciences and the arts is named neuroaesthetics [44].
155 Discussion on the impact of art on the brain can be found in [45]. Further, they developed an approach that applies evidence-based brain science research methods to arts, architecture, and music interventions. Transmission [46] is a research project that creates alternate representations of neural activity through sound and vision, and it investigates the effect of interaction on human consciousness. The two-users experience enables a new form of interactivity by
160 translating both neurological processes and kinetic dynamics into a new form. Another work that uses puzzle games as a mental stimulator is presented in [47]. Participant's electrical brain activities are connected with a display system of puzzle pieces via an electroencephalogram (EEG) system. This work reveals
165 the possibility of analyzing interactive processes quantitatively by interpreting neural dimensions in interactive arts. In [48], conducted study addresses how aesthetic evaluation of dance is related to perceived physical ability to reproduce watched dance movements. What happens in our brains when we observe someone performing a dance sequence or how do we understand action or movement
170 are some of the questions answered in [49].

3. Methods and Materials

3.1. Similarity of Dancing Performances

Motion capture data were collected using an optical motion capture system with passive markers, OptiTrack [50] and its corresponding software, Motive. The frame rate was set to 120 frames per second. Professional dancers were recorded during previously held recording sessions described in [51]. In the experiment presented in this article, participants were wearing suits with markers during the learning and performing phase. After putting on a suit, participants were instructed by the experimenter to move to the center of the recording area and stand in a T-pose, so it was possible to create their skeleton. T-Pose is a default pose for a 3D model’s skeleton before it is animated [52]. Also, at the beginning of the recording, participants had to take the T-pose, and afterward, they were able to start with the learning phase and move in the recording area. For the performing phase, the procedure was as follows. Participants were asked to stand in T-pose and the recording started. After that, they had to move to the position where they wanted to start dancing. The experimenter played music, and they performed the learned dance. The procedure was repeated three times in each session.

In this work, DTW was used for comparison of the user’s data with professional dancer’s data. DTW is a well-known technique for finding an optimal alignment between two sequences and it is often used for synchronization of motions. Since the recorded data do not have the same length and they vary in timing, we decided to use this approach. Similarities between the two compared motions are calculated and stored in the cost matrix. The matrix can be calculated as shown in Eq. 1 [9]:

$$DTW(i, j) = d(a_i, b_j) + \min \begin{cases} D(i-1, j) \\ D(i, j-1) \\ D(i-1, j-1) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $DTW(i, j)$ is the node associated with a_i and b_j . Further, distance

$d(a_i, b_j)$ is calculated as:

$$d(a_i, b_j) = (a_i - b_j)^2 \quad (2)$$

If two motions are similar, then the distance between them will be small (low cost); otherwise, the distance is large (high cost) [53]. The main goal is to find an optimal alignment between signals with minimal overall cost. DTW can be applied for multidimensional signals and quaternions as well.

In general, in DTW, one signal is a template (reference) signal, while the other is a test signal [54]. DTW for quaternions (QDTW) can be used for time-signals of rotations that are described by quaternions, which is the case for the motion capture data. Also, signals from the professional dancers are used as a template for DTW, while the data from the participants are used as test signals. Quaternions can be defined as a four-dimensional entity:

$$q = [w, (x, y, z)] = w + ix + jy + kz \quad (3)$$

The cost function for QDTW can be defined as follows [55]:

$$d(x, y) = 1 - (x \cdot y) \quad (4)$$

where \cdot is a dot product and x and y are normalized quaternions. DTW has time and space complexity $O(n, m)$, where n and m are lengths of compared signals.

In this work, the Eq. 2 was used to find the distance between quaternions in successive frames in order to determine the rotation change over time and get the trajectory for each body joint. This was done for professionals' and participants' data. Further, the data for corresponding joint trajectories are compared using DTW and the final score is calculated as the average value of all distances for each body joint. The described workflow is shown in Fig. 2. In [56], DTW is used to determine the similarity between any two segments, while in [6], DTW is applied to the extracted features of two motions. In [57], the concept of similarity, together with the learned features for searching similar occurrences of interested actions within a long motion sequence, is presented.

Figure 2: Workflow for data analysis.

Figure 3: Male and female avatars.

3.2. AR Application

The AR application used for the experiment was implemented using Unity3D and presented in [58]. The application is implemented based on the ARCore platform. Motion tracking, light estimation and environmental understanding are provided in ARCore. Additionally, flat surfaces, e.g., floor, can be detected by ARCore and this feature is used in our implementation. Both groups used the same application. The folk dance, named Krebspolka, with male and female versions, was added to the application (see Fig. 3). Animations from the professional dancers were exported and attached to the avatars.

Participants used the application in landscape mode on mobile phone placed

in Google cardboard. During the first part of the learning phase, participants could switch between two different modes; step-by-step and steps together. The dance consists of stamp step, galop and polka step [59]. In the second part of the learning phase, participants had to watch and learn the whole dance. Functionalities like play/pause, switch between steps, play forward/reward and slow down were available in order to help participants to adjust the learning procedure to their pace. Also, they could move in the environment to observe avatars from different viewpoints and different angles. Participants interacted with the application using swipe gestures. The experimenter changed the avatar according to the gender of the participant (e.g., female avatar for female participants) before the experiment started.

3.3. Stimulation Session

For the tDCS, Neuroelectronics Startsim [60] was used. Stimulation was done by using two circular sponge electrodes soaked in saline. The area of one electrode was approximately 20 cm². According to the International 10-20 system, the anode was placed on Cz, which corresponds to vertex, and it is placed over midline central brain regions. The cathode was placed on the forehead, FPZ position. The anode is placed near the vertex to simultaneously facilitate the primary motor cortex (M1) since this brain area is involved in motor function. In our experiment, the stimulation was applied prior to each learning session. The setup for tDCS for the experiment presented in this work is shown in Fig. 4. Fig. 5 shows a participant during the stimulation session. In the literature, the current is usually 1-2 mA and the stimulation are 10-20 minutes long. In this study, the current was 1250 mA and, in each session, stimulation was 20 minutes long with 30 seconds long ramp-up and ramp-down, at the beginning and in the end, respectively. For the sham group, the procedure consisted of 30 seconds long ramp-up at the beginning and ramp down in the end. The setup and length of this part were the same as for the stimulation group to keep blinding for the participants.

Figure 4: Electrodes used for tDCS in the experiment presented in this article.

Figure 5: Stimulation setup during the experiment.

3.4. Experiment

In total, ten healthy people without previous knowledge of the dance, participated in the experiment, 6 males and 4 females. All participants are between 22–31 years old and each of them attended three sessions on three different days within a week. Before sessions had started, participants were randomly assigned to two groups that received sham stimulation or tDCS. There were 5 participants in each group. Each participant received the same stimulation type in all three sessions and did not know which type of stimulation they received. One group received stimulation, tDCS, 20 minutes long, while the other group received sham, also for 20 minutes. In case of sham stimulation, stimulation was on for a very short time and this does not make any changes in the brain. After the stimulation part was done, participants were asked to put on a suit with markers and they were given instructions on how to use the application. In each session participants had one minute to try the application on their own and try to memorize commands. Training included two parts: learning steps and learning the whole dance. During the first session, participants had 15 minutes to learn and practice steps and 10 minutes to watch and learn the whole dance. The second session was 12.5 minutes long for steps and 7.5 minutes long for the whole dance. The third session was 10 minutes for steps and 5 minutes for the whole dance. Once the learning session is done, participants had to perform the dance three times only with music playing.

In the experiment six questionnaires were used. Before the experiment started, participants had to read information about the experiment and sign the consent form. They also had to fill a short version of Points of relevance with known influence on the outcome of TES checklist. This checklist increases the reproducibility of studies, minimizes deviations from a given protocol and diminishes variability. The next questionnaire they had to fill before the experiment started was the Screening questionnaire for transcranial electrical stimulation (TES) [61]. Participants were instructed to notify the experimenter if answer to any question in this questionnaire was affirmative so the experimenter could balance the risk-benefit ratio and decide whether to continue the exper-

iment. The pre-exposure simulator sickness questionnaire (Pre-SSQ) was also used. This questionnaire includes a list of symptoms rated on a scale from 0 = 'None' to 3 = 'Severe'. Participants filled the same questionnaire (Post-SSQ) at the end of the experiment. Using the SSQ questionnaire it is possible to measure sickness in the context of simulation and it was derived from a measure of motion sickness. Several representative scores like nausea related sub-score (N), oculomotor related sub-score (O), disorientation related sub-score (D) and total score (TS) can be calculated from SSQ [62]. Once the experiment was done, except Post-SSQ, participants were asked to fill the Presence Questionnaire (PQ) [63], NASA-TLX [64], and the Questionnaire of sensations related to transcranial electrical stimulation. PQ consists of 24 questions with a seven-point scale, where 1 = 'Not at all' to 7 = 'Completely'. Participants had to answer 22 questions; since there was no haptic feedback, those questions were skipped. Again, several scores can be calculated according to [63]. NASA-TLX was used to evaluate cognitive workload. It includes six questions on 21-point scale, ranging from low to very high for mental, physical and temporal demand, effort and frustration and perfect to failure for performance. The Questionnaire of sensations related to TES is a questionnaire on the intensity and frequency of adverse events. It increases safety when tDCS is used and it is a recommended procedure for publication of TES experiments. Scale for discomfort during the electrical stimulation was from 0 = 'None' to 3 = 'Strong'. A debriefing session was performed at the end of the experiment in written form. Participants were asked to share their comments and impressions. The order of male and female participants and types of stimulation was also randomized throughout the experiment. The duration of the experiment was dependent on the session, and it was 60-90 minutes. This study was approved by The Research Ethics Committee of Masaryk University (reference number EKV-2019-067).

4. Results

320 4.1. Motion Data Analysis

Participants were divided into two groups based on the type of stimulation they received; tDCS or sham. For each participant in each session, three scores have been calculated and the best one was chosen for further analysis. Mixed Factorial ANOVA was applied since we needed to analyze a mixture of between-
325 group and repeated measures variables. Before we start with analysis, there are few assumptions that should be met before repeated measures ANOVA can be applied. One of the assumptions is that the distribution of the dependent variable should be approximately normally distributed. To check this requirement Shapiro-Wilk test of normality has been applied on scores and results are shown
330 in Table1. The analysis is done using IBM SPSS Statistics.

Table 1: Shapiro-Wilk Test of Normality.

Session	Type of Stimulation	Sig.
First Session	Sham	0.172
	tDCS	0.794
Second Session	Sham	0.645
	tDCS	0.936
Third Session	Sham	0.671
	tDCS	0.260

In Table 1, it is visible that Sig. value is greater than 0.05 and the data have a normal distribution. Further, ANOVA using a repeated measures design was conducted. Table 2 shows descriptive statistics for all sessions and types of stimulation. The results show that the group that received tDCS has a lower
335 mean score, which means that in general they performed better in all three sessions. Also, the standard deviation is smaller, which means that results within the group are similar. The best session is the second, where mean values are the lowest for both groups. All participants performed better in the second

Table 2: Descriptive statistics.

Session	Type of Stimulation	Mean	Std. Deviation
First Session	Sham	8791.0539	1552.65683
	tDCS	6839.2860	898.94030
	Total	7815.1699	1577.58051
Second Session	Sham	7699.0054	856.36816
	tDCS	6278.3982	296.20112
	Total	6988.7018	962.04172
Third Session	Sham	8079.2975	1154.65407
	tDCS	6294.1604	318.10252
	Total	7186.7289	1233.98391

session than in the first. Only three participants had the best score in the third
340 session.

Another assumption for repeated measure ANOVA is sphericity; the vari-
ances of the differences between all combinations of related groups must be
equal. Mauchly's Test of Sphericity is a formal way of testing this assumption.
Results of the test are statistically significant for our data, $p=0.016$ ($p < 0.05$),
345 $\chi^2(2) = 8.234$, which means that we accept the alternative hypothesis that the
variances of the differences are not equal, and sphericity has been violated. It
means that certain corrections have to be made. Mean scores for both Session
main effect ($F(1.182, 9.459)=3.505$, $p=0.088$) and Session x Type of Stimulation
interaction ($F(1.182, 9.459)=0.347$, $p=0.605$) when using repeated measures
350 with Greenhouse-Geisser correction are not statistically significantly different.

The next step is to check the assumption of homogeneity of variance. This
is done using Levene's test. This test's significant values are non-significant for
each session ($p=0.510$, $p=0.052$ and $p=0.060$ respectively for scores from the
first, second and third session). This indicates that the variances are homoge-
355 neous for all levels of the repeated measures variables. Now we can proceed
with analysis for the main effect of type of stimulation. Results show significant

effect, $F(1, 18) = 13.237$, $p=0.007$. This means that if we ignore all other variables, participants that received tDCS were significantly different from participants that received sham stimulation. Even though the sample is small, this
360 confirms our hypothesis that participants that received tDCS will learn better the dance. In Fig. 6, mean values for each session and both groups can be seen. From the graph, we can see that group that received tDCS performed better in all three sessions. Also, both groups had better results in the second session. The difference between second and third sessions for the tDCS group is
365 smaller than for the sham group, which means their results between these two sessions were similar. Experimental results confirm the hypothesis and indicate that these participants performed the dance significantly better compared to the sham group. Also, we expected participants to have the best scores in the third session. Results did not confirm this expectation, and participants had the best
370 scores in the second session. However, these results encourage the extension and continuation of the research in this direction.

4.2. Questionnaires Evaluation

The first part of the analysis was done using Spearman's rank-order correlation to determine the relationship between scores from questionnaires and
375 scores calculated from motion data. In the second session, there is a positive correlation between Self-evaluation and Possibility to examine scores ($r_s=0.635$, $p=0.048$). Results from the third session show that there is a positive correlation between score calculated from motion data and Possibility to act ($r_s=0.690$, $p=0.027$).

380 According to results from NASA-TLX, there is a strong negative correlation between score calculated from motion data and Temporal demand ($r_s=-0.746$, $p=0.013$) in the first session. Furthermore, the t-test and Mann-Whitney test, dependent on data distribution, were used to analyze scores between groups (sham or tDCS). Only significant differences were found in the first session for
385 Quality of interface score ($p=0.015$) and for Realism score in the third session ($p=0.034$). Participants who received tDCS had all scores lower than the sham

Figure 6: Mean values for scores in each session for both groups.

group in all three sessions, except for Sounds score in the first session. The environment for them was less realistic and they evaluated themselves to be less successful in performance.

390 When it comes to the comparison for all participants between sessions, shown in Fig. 7, there is an increase in all scores. As participants used the application more, they also gave higher scores for the AR environment and for their performance.

395 From the comparison of mean scores between sessions for NASA-TLX scores, shown in Fig. 8, mental demand, physical demand, and frustration were lower in the last session. Their estimation of the performance is in line with results from motion capture data.

From Pre-SSQ and Post-SSQ results, shown in Fig. 9, except for Oculomotor score in the third session, all scores were higher after the experiment was

Figure 7: Comparison of mean scores between sessions (PQ).

Figure 8: Comparison of mean scores between sessions (NASA-TLX).

400 done, indicating that participants experienced symptoms stronger when the experiment was done.

Regarding qualitative feedback, participants rated this experiment as an interesting experience. They found the application useful and interesting. One

Figure 9: Comparison of mean scores between sessions (Pre-SSQ and Post-SSQ).

participant wrote that he had a feeling that he was learning the dance. Also,
 405 participants considered examination of the dance from different viewpoints and
 the possibility to change the speed very useful and helpful. One participant
 considered the experiment well organized. Two participants reported that it was
 difficult for them to dance with the headset. Three participants reported that
 they could not locate the avatar during the spinning step. For one participant,
 410 music was too loud. Participants suggested the implementation of instructions
 on how to interact with the application and providing feedback.

5. Discussion

The main goal of this article was to examine the effect of tDCS on folk dance
 learning process and performance. For visual feedback, a mobile AR application
 415 was used. This is the first time the effect of non-invasive brain stimulation on
 folk dance performance was investigated.

According to the analysis of motion data, participants that received stimu-
 lation performed significantly better than the participants in the sham group.
 This is the most important result of the study and confirmation of our hypoth-

420 esis. Also, the standard deviation of the scores calculated from motion capture data for the tDCS group was lower compared to the sham group. This indicates the scores tend to be close to the mean value and clustered close to it. It has been presented in the literature that the tDCS can be effective for motor learning tasks [65, 31].

425 A learning curve is a representation of the relationship between proficiency in some tasks and experience. As we gain experience, we are getting better at performing the task [66]. In [67, 68], authors explored the efficiency of using 3D animations for dance learning, and the results show potential for using this kind of application. Our results are in line with those works. In our experiment,
430 DTW was used for data analysis. In this case, a lower score means higher similarity between compared signals, and therefore, it is expected for the learning curve to decline throughout the sessions. All participants performed better in the second session, and even though it was expected to have the best performances in the third session, according to the learning curve, that was not the
435 case. A possible reason is that they were already saturated with the learning since the sessions were held within seven days, or they overestimated themselves and thought they do not need more practice. However, participants performed better in later sessions compared to the first one. Applying tDCS can sustain and enhance motor learning and accelerate improvements in motor learning [69].
440 Although all participants managed to remember the dance, three sessions are not enough for learning.

A positive correlation between scores calculated from motion capture data and the possibility to act was found. Possibility to act score included questions like how much participants were able to control events or how responsive the
445 environment was to the performed actions. The higher possibility to act and to control the environment resulted in better performance. If participants feel control over the application, they can direct their attention to the task and not the application itself. Furthermore, participants from the tDCS group estimated themselves to be less successful in a final performance. Since this result is
450 obtained from questionnaires, it is subjective and dependant on participants'

self-confidence. Immediate feedback and score how successful they were can increase their confidence.

According to average scores from all participants, there is an increase in all subscores from PQ. The more they used the application, the more realistic the
455 AR environment was for them. They also estimated themselves to be more successful in performance in the second and third session than in the first one. In the literature [70, 71], it has been reported that a higher sense of presence in a virtual environment might contribute to learning. Regarding results from SSQ questionnaires, participants had higher scores after the experiment. This
460 was expected since they were immersed in the virtual environment, and the task included movements.

Although questionnaires are difficult to interpret and subjective, we managed to find correlations and present results. The sample of ten participants is small for traditional studies. However, in this experiment, there were three sessions
465 for each participant. Also, typical studies with tDCS are usually in this range of sample sizes.

This study's limitations, except for the number of sessions, include the number of dances and only one virtual environment without feedback. Participants had to learn only one dance that was approximately 2 minutes long, and it
470 would be good to compare if participants can learn more dances and more complicated dances this way. Also, comparison with other environments, e.g., VR, 3D or video, and comparison with feedback provided, could help understand how it affects the learning and performing process. Further, participants said they would appreciate having instructions for interaction with the application,
475 although they had one minute to practice and get familiar with the application. In the future, we should investigate other ways of giving instructions and make the application easier to use. Some participants said they could not see the avatar during some movements, i.e., spinning, and it was difficult for them to track the movements. In the future, we should focus on having an avatar all the
480 time within the field of view.

As it has been already mentioned, dance is a performing art. In the literature

[72, 73, 74], EEG has been used for measuring brain activity during dance imagery tasks. In [75, 76], functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) helped to investigate neural mechanisms that underlie the interpretation of dance choreography. Besides numerical analysis and comparison, mentioned methods can
485 be used to investigate how folk dances affect our brain. This certainly represents interesting guidelines for future research.

6. Conclusion

In this article, we presented the dance learning process using AR application in combination with tDCS since tDCS has been used for the enhancement of
490 motor learning. Recently, AR and VR applications have found their use in dance learning, but still not many applications are available, and this article also contributes from that point of view. Participants in the experiment had a task to learn a folk dance using an augmented reality application. They were divided
495 into two groups, marked as sham and tDCS. TDCS was applied prior to the learning part of the experiment. Once the learning part was done, participants performed the dance only with music, and motion data were collected using an optical motion capture system. Each participant attended three learning sessions. Based on motion data analysis using the DTW algorithm, there is a
500 statistically significant difference in performances between the sham and tDCS group. Although the sample is small, 10 participants, these results support the continuation of the research in this direction and open a new perspective on the combination of tDCS and dance learning. Results from the questionnaires show that participants were able to learn how to use and control the application.
505 They did not spend much time learning the interaction, which was one of our goals. The learning process in each session included two phases, learning steps and learning the whole dance. All participants managed to remember the dance and perform it at the end of each session, with only music playing. Although motion sickness might represent a problem when motion is combined with virtual
510 environments, none of the participants experienced very strong symptoms that

would have resulted in the interruption of the experiment. In the debriefing session, participants expressed their very positive impressions, and they enjoyed the experiment. This result supports the idea of using AR applications for dance learning and its combination with tDCS, which can be used in the future with
515 different use cases than folk dances.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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